

High-throughput immunofluorescence to validate high-affinity binders

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Protocol description

Protocol for high-throughput evaluation of binder candidates. The protocol can be used for the permeabilization assessment by an adaption of the blocking solution.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ 1st antibody:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ anti-HA rat (Roche # 11867423001).▪ 2nd antibody:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ anti-Rat Alexafluor 488 (goat anti-rat IgG: Invitrogen #A1106).○ FLAG-M2-Cy3 conjugated (Sigma-Aldrich#A9594).▪ High-affinity binders (nanobodies, sybodies, scFABs...).▪ HEK293 Jump-in T-rex cells (TFS).▪ HCT116 cells (ATCC)
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Poly-L-lysine (Sigma #P6282).▪ Counter-staining Hoechst 33342 (TFS # 62249).▪ 100 % Triton-X (Sigma #9036-19-5).▪ Formaldehyde 37% (Merck #1040021000).
Equipment:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Opera Phenix[®] Plus HCS System (Perkin Elmer).

Reagents setup

Blocking solution (fresh!): 10% FCS + 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS (1x).

Calculate the amount needed for the experiment. For 200 mL: mix 180 mL PBS (1x), 20ml FCS and 0.6 mL 100% Triton-X (better to make 20 % stock in H₂O/ or PBS as 100 % Triton is difficult to pipette).

Blocking solution without detergent: 10% FCS in PBS (1x) for non-permeabilization conditions.

PFA (fresh!): 4% FA in PBS (1x).

For 37 mL: mix 4 mL Formaldehyde 37% and 33 mL PBS (1x).

Poly-L-lysine: Sigma #P6282.

Plates coated with Poly-L-lysine (for HEK293 cells only) can be prepared the day before and stored at 4°C (*Note 1*).

Antibodies:

1st AB:

- a-HA – Roche (rat) 1:1000 in blocking solution (4C).

2nd AB:

- Rat Alexa-fluor 488 use 1:500 in blocking solution (IF box 4C).
- FLAG-M2-Cy3 conjugated 1:500 in blocking solution.

Counter stain solution.

Use Hoechst 33342 1:1000 in PBS (1x).

Procedure

▪ Cell seeding / day 1:

1. For OE cells:
 - Seed 100 µl medium with 20,000 cells / well
 - Induce protein expression by adding 100 µl DMEM 10%FBS, 1% P/S medium containing 2 µg/ml Dox (i.e 1 µg/ml Dox final concentration).
 - Incubate 24 h at 37°C.
2. For the non-induced: leave the 100 µl medium / well from the split (that should be sufficient).
3. Incubate 24 h at 37°C

▪ Cell fixation and immunofluorescence staining / day 2:

4. Aspirate medium carefully using a yellow tip.
5. Do not wash cells in PBS.
6. Fix cells with 50 µl PFA solution for 15 min rocking at RT.
7. Properly dispose of fixation solution (appropriate waste container).
8. Add 50 µl ml blocking solution and incubate for 1h rocking @ RT.
9. Add 30 µl / well of blocking solution supplemented with primary antibody (note 2) or binders (we tested final conc. of 33 and 100 µg/ml (note 3)) at the right concentration(s). Incubate for 2h @ RT or o/n at 4°C and rocking.
10. Wash very gently 1x 15 min, 2 x 5 min, in 50 µl / well blocking solution, rocking at RT.
11. Add 30 µl of blocking solution supplemented with secondary antibody for 1 h, rocking at RT.
12. Wash very gently 1x 15min followed by 2x 5 min in 50 µl / well blocking solution rocking.
13. Counter stain with 30 µl / well Hoechst diluted 1:1000 in PBS (1x) 10 min @ RT rocking and leave it there.
14. Cover the plate with aluminum foil and put at 4° C dark room for imaging in the Opera Phenix using appropriate channels.

Additional notes

Note 1: Do not trash the PLL, you can recycle it.

Note 2: Calculate carefully the total volume of needed antibodies to not waste them.

Note 3: It is key to centrifuge binders in the table centrifuge at full speed and 4 °C. Then take supernatant and re-aliquot. Finally prepare then master mix in blocking buffer at the desired concentration.

Suggested layout for 96 well plates:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	Binder conc. ug/ml
A	DE cell + dxw	100											
B	DE cell - dxw	100											
C	DE cell + dxw	33											
D	DE cell - dxw	33											
E													
F													
G											2nd AB only	DE cell + dxw	
H											2nd AB only	DE cell - dxw	
Binder	Binder_1	Binder_2	Binder_3	Binder_4	Binder_5	Binder_6	Binder_7	Binder_8	Binder_9	Binder_10	Binder_11	Binder_12	

Data availability

<https://re-solute.eu/resources/reagents>

References

Please write to contact@re-solute.eu in case of questions or errors.